

WHY ACADEMIC VOCABULARY IS IMPORTANT AND HOW TO MASTER IT?

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Abstract.

In modern times, more and more people are learning English. This language has become a means of international communication, almost all literature is written in it, conferences are held and all world news in any field is also written in English. It is for this reason that this language is becoming more and more popular, more and more people want to learn it, and sometimes not only for communication but also for academic or professional purposes. In this article review, various methods of studying the lexical part of the language, studied by various scientists from completely different parts of the world, their effectiveness and, conversely, uselessness, will be considered, various examples of studies showing the effectiveness of one method or another will be given. A little information will also be given about what problems students face during the study of vocabulary, why this happens, and how to deal with it.

Why vocabulary is important?

Blachowicz (2013) noted in one of her works that the study of any school discipline develops knowledge not only of the subject itself but also forces students to learn new vocabulary and develop the language, although sometimes this can turn out to be an obstacle for them. Most of the lexical items that they encounter while studying physics, mathematics, the humanities, etc., are unfamiliar and unusual to them. They rarely use them, and in some cases have never heard of them. These words are called academic vocabulary or vocabulary of the professional field. Also, she noted that vocabulary develops only if the teacher pays attention to these words, and explains
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their meaning and use, thereby helping students to learn them. Also, she draws attention to the fact that students should regularly expose themselves to the use of language in speech, writing, and the study of new areas of knowledge. The teacher should show them different methods and teach them how to use them. As an example, she provides concepts such as "receptive vocabulary" and "expressive vocabulary".

Most students have a purely positive attitude toward the study of academic vocabulary. Students realize that a strong vocabulary helps them in their studies, and they better understand academic material, articles, and lectures, Yanti (2018) wrote about this. He also provided evidence that the confident use of academic vocabulary strengthened their belief in academic success and the ability to acquire knowledge to the fullest. Also, knowledge of words helped them in self-study, which led to a sharp increase in their academic performance, writes Cita Hikmah Yanti (2018).

Of course, language proficiency is determined by vocabulary proficiency. In one of his works, Naeem Afzal (2019) noted that expanding the vocabulary is very important, but it is important not only for a person learning a second or foreign language but even for those for whom English is native. With all this, the studied words bring a sufficient number of problems and trials into the educational routine, all of which have completely different reasons. It also significantly affects student performance, most students learning in a second language simply do not have enough vocabulary to maintain academic performance at the level of university education notes Afzal (2019).

Liping Wei (2021) fully agrees with Afzal's point of view and notes that the student is faced with a double study load - learning a second language and material provided by an educational institution, which leads to several problems and difficulties. Students face a number of unpleasant situations. They try to maintain communication and at the same time keep up with their peers. With all their efforts, they most often fail to cope with both tasks. Everyone knows that academic vocabulary is closely related to academic performance. Academic vocabulary is the key to communication

in the classroom and is crucial in learning content, as students use only academic language in the learning process.

Issues while learning terminology.

(Tozcu & Coady, 2004) conducted studies. These studies are devoted to the study of vocabulary in four stages: discrimination, understanding, memorization, consolidation, and expansion of meanings. The first stage involves the distinction between sound and letter. It helps to speak, read and write, and most importantly, listen because sounds are valued, students learn to pronounce words correctly and demand them, which eliminates problems in communication and the presence of context. The second stage involves understanding and meaning of words by associating them with their speakers. The third stage - the memorization stage consists of the ability to retain values in memory and use them in the right Professional and at the right time. The fourth stage includes the possibility of learning new vocabulary and differentiating the useful and necessary from the vocabulary, which will quickly go into the passive vocabulary. (Grauberg, 1997). However, the study of vocabulary usually becomes an unbearable burden for students, it constantly becomes the development of the language, the language is dynamic and constantly replenished, and enriched with the indicated points, which is often almost impossible to cope with. it becomes that when learning a language, various techniques and methods are not used, as, for example, when studying grammar. Students usually just memorize hundreds of words and quickly forget them.

Baniabdelrahman (2014), used various techniques and conducted a study among first-year students. Students had to guess words that were previously unfamiliar to them. They were given a text that they had to read and try to understand what each word could stand for. The results of the work showed that this technique failed and most of the students could not use this technique. This work showed that practice is the best way to teach academic vocabulary and that institutions should motivate teachers to use practical strategies to learn new vocabulary.

Altayri (2017) also supports the position of the aforementioned scientists and believes that students' weak abilities indicate their poor vocabulary. The researcher
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points to two reliable facts that are the cause of poor vocabulary learning and vocabulary insufficiency of students in state institutions. The results of his research indicate that students use vocabulary strategies inefficiently, for example, they mainly use a bilingual dictionary simply by translating words and do not understand their full meaning. Similarly, the results also point to insufficient use of English and the practice of lexical units. The author recommends a step-by-step process of learning vocabulary.

With all of the above, Farjami and Aidinlou (2013) noticed that learning a foreign or second language proficiency requires a large amount of words, but this requires considerable effort to capture the words in your long-term memory. In this work, the problems of students in the study of vocabulary were also considered and some teaching and learning methods were proposed so that these problems could be solved. The author also focuses on the methods of long-term vocabulary, and pays less attention to the study of short-term ones. It is because of this that Fargami and Aidinlow offer a practical approach to augmenting familiar words. They believe that teachers should present the newest vocabulary units in context and give students hints to guess the meanings (Farjami & Aidinlou, 2013).

How to learn effectively?

It becomes clear that students have access to the content of the teacher only with sufficient vocabulary. Long-term studies have confirmed this: there is a strong relationship between students' vocabulary knowledge and their learning success.

Reading is one of the most effective ways to increase your vocabulary. Nagy, Anderson and Herman (1987) showed that students who brushed increased their vocabulary more than those who did not read.

But while this output is impressive, it is not required to successfully use the amount of vocabulary. This is why Nagy (1988) came to the conclusion that the best way to learn vocabulary is when students associate words with source and base words, think of similar terminology in order to recognize unfamiliar words. Being informed about how words function gives way to many words that would otherwise not be understood.

How can a teacher help in the study of academic terminology? Some research proves the need to create an academic vocabulary, but some teachers still do not pay attention to this and do not consider it important. An observational study found that the teacher did not take the time to study academic vocabulary, and also did not pay enough attention to respectful vocabulary in general.

Considering the small amount of time that most teachers devote to helping students develop vocabulary, it is imperative to make that time as efficient as possible.

But how can we make a more effective model of teaching academic vocabulary for language learners. We will start with "protected learning", an approach to learning that integrates language and content learning. In "protected learning", students are protected from language requirements that are beyond their understanding. Essentially, it is teaching content at the group level.

Peregoy and Boyle (2017) talked about a couple of main sources of word learning - random learning and explicit learning. Incidental learning is learning using language in communicative contexts, such as communication, independent reading, etc. e. Explicit learning includes identifying new knowledge as well as statistics, memorization and use of new words (Peregoy & Boyle, 2017, p. 260).

It is very important to teach vocabulary using strategies that involve students in learning new words. When teaching a new word, the definition of the lexical definition follows, since dictionary definitions often include other words. Instead, the teacher follows the students' description or review of the words. Repetition is the mother of learning. Ask students to repeat everything aloud. Then ask them to use that word. Students can work in pairs. This option can be repeated with each selected word. When teaching academic vocabulary using this cycle, the defense of the material is repeated. After activities are developed, before students have the opportunity to practice terminology. different strategies are prescribed, the study of new vocabulary should be stimulated. Learning vocabulary through reading may not be enough, teaching vocabulary directly provides greater opportunities for academic success.

Conclusion.

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In today's world of education, there is diversity, all teachers should prepare their own curriculum and instructions, maximize student opportunities, improve the level of English language proficiency. Non-native learners tend to have a lower rate than their peers for using English as a native language, and there are many explanations for this. The vocabulary pursued for each subject presents an insurmountable challenge, as it takes time and effort even for native speakers to master highly specialized academic vocabulary. This article changes how a teacher can help English learners with curative academic vocabulary. Learning vocabulary is a complex process and vocabulary must be allergenic, studied and protected on an ongoing basis.

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